

Effect of calcium peroxide coating on yield and yield attributes of Jaya

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In flooded soils, where germination and seedling establishment of direct-seeded rice are poor, coating seeds with calcium peroxide may improve germination rate and crop yield. During 1981-82 winter, Jaya was used to study the effect of peroxide coating on yield and yield attributes in puddled and submerged (6-10 cm standing water) plantings. Three levels of calcium peroxide coating – 0, 20, and 40% – were evaluated.

In submerged plots, number of

Effect of calcium peroxide seed coating on yield and yield attributes of rice. ^a

Treatment	Panicles/m ²	Panicle weight (g)	Grains/panicle	Panicle length (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Puddled</i>					
Noncoated	390 a	2.5 a	75 a	22 a	4.5 a
20% coating	398 bc	3.3 b	90 a	23 a	4.8 a
40% coating	401 c	3.6 bc	93 b	24 bc	4.9 a
<i>Submerged</i>					
Noncoated	394 b	3.0 ab	88 a	22 a	4.5 a
20% coating	401 c	3.0 ab	92 b	23 b	5.3 b
40% coating	410	3.9 c	108 b	25 c	5.5 b

^aMeans followed by the same letter do not differ significantly.

panicles, panicle weight, number of grains per panicle, and panicle length increased significantly with 40% peroxide coating (see table). Except for number of panicles, all yield attributes at 40% peroxide coating were similar in puddled and sub-

merged fields. Yield was highest for 40% coating under submergence, followed by 20% coating. Higher yields in submerged fields were probably due to improved oxygen supply to plants at early growth stage. □

Effect of preplanting submergence and seedling age on wetland rice yield

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Farmers of the Cauvery Delta commonly believe that preparing fields and keeping them continuously submerged for at least a month before planting increases rice yield. This system was tested at TRRI during 1982 kharif.

The field was plowed twice with a tractor-drawn cage wheel 15 days before transplanting, leveled, and kept under continuous preplanting submergence. Yields from this field were compared with those of a similarly prepared field that was tilled on the day of trans-

Effect of preplanting submergence and seedling age on rice grain yield, Aduthurai, India.

Seedling age (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Preplanting submergence	Control	Mean
25	5.3	4.0	4.7
30	4.8	3.5	4.2
35	4.7	3.5	4.1
40	4.3	2.9	3.6
Mean	4.8	3.5	–
CD (0.05) for submergence	1.08		
CD (0.05) for seedling age	0.43		
Interactions	ns		

planting. Short-duration (105 d) rice variety TKM9 was raised with seedlings of 4 ages in subplots. Treatments were thrice replicated. Plots were harvested individually and yield was recorded at 14% moisture level.

Preplanting submergence gave significantly higher yield irrespective of seedling age (see table). In both fields, 25-day-old seedlings yielded best (see table). As seedling age increased, yield decreased particularly at 40 days of age. □

Sexual propagation of azolla through the sporocarp

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Azolla usually multiplies by vegetative propagation; however, sexual reproduction, which is essential to the survival of the population during temporary adverse conditions, also occurs. Our experiments

indicate the fertilized egg (zygote) undergoes a 2- to 3-month dormancy period.

Fresh and matured megasporocarps and microsporocarps were inoculated in Watanabe's nutrient medium for azolla and incubated under artificial light (3000 lux) with controlled $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ temperature. Sporocarps germinated after 3 months. In the field, sporocarps produced in Mar germinated in Jun when day temperature ranged from 25 to 35°C . Azolla also had a 3-month dormancy period in field nurseries.

Azolla microspores and megasporocarps do not germinate until they are liberated from the sporangia. Fertilization occurs only in water. The zygote formed after fertilization is deposited on the soil surface where it undergoes dormancy.

We adopted the following procedure to break the dormancy period and induce azolla germination. Fresh azolla with sporocarps were inoculated into potted soil with 1 cm deep water. When water evaporated, azolla deposited on the soil surface dried, leaving zygotes. The top

2.5 cm of soil was removed and dried either in a hot air oven at 60°C for 24 hours or in sunlight for 2 to 3 days, This soil was used as inoculant. Normally, zygotes sprout into small seedlings 10 to 15 days after inoculation and mature

sporophytes develop within 20-25 days. The oven-dried zygotes germinated within 10-12 days; sun-dried zygotes germinated in 18-20 days.

The laboratory method allows researchers to raise azolla fronds from dried

materials and to transport azolla seed inoculum (dried zygotes), without damaging seed viability. This technique may also solve storage problems, sowing limitations imposed by summer, and help in azolla crossbreeding. □

Effect of summer plowing with different implements on wetland rice yields

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The effect of summer plowing with different implements on wetland rice yield and weed dry matter accumulation was studied during 1980 and 1981. Treatments were no tillage (control), plowing with country plow, tractor-drawn 11-tined cultivator, and tractor-drawn disc plow. Land was tilled in April and rice was transplanted in early July after puddling with a 10-hp power tiller. Soil was a sandy clay loam.

Plots tilled by disc plow had lowest weed population and yielded highest (see table). Weed dry matter accumulation was lowest after disc plowing,

Effect of summer plowing with different implements on rice gain yield and weed dry matter accumulation.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)			Weed dry matter accumulation (t/ha)		
	1980	1981	Mean	1980	1981	Mean
Control	2.4	2.0	2.2	2.1	2.7	2.4
Country plow	2.8	2.1	2.4	1.7	2.0	1.8
Cultivator	3.1	2.2	2.6	1.5	1.6	1.5
Disc plow	3.8	2.6	3.2	0.9	1.2	1.1
Mean	3.0	2.2	2.6	1.5	1.9	1.7
CD at 5%	0.1	0.2		0.1	0.04	

amounting to 0.9 t/ha in 1980 and 1.2 t/ha in 1981, followed by values for the cultivator and country plow.

Weed flora consisted mostly of *Cyperus rotundus* L., *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv., *Monochoria hastata* (L.) Solms, *Paspalum scrobiculatum* L., *Panicum* spp., *Hygrophila spinosa* T. Anders., *Oxalis* spp., *Emilia sonchifolia*

(L.) DC. ex Wight, *Setaria glauca* (L.) Beauv., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers., *Sporobolus diander* (Retz.) Beauv., *Chrysopogon* spp., *Caesulia axillaris* Roxb., *Saponaria vaccaria* L., *Spergula arvensis* L., *Jussiaea suffruticosa* L., *Polygonum plebeium* R. Br., and *Ageratum conyzoides* L., in decreasing order of population. □

Response of irrigated dry seeded rice to nitrogen level, interrow spacing, and seeding rate in a semiarid environment

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Semiarid soils are inherently nitrogen deficient, which limits rice yields. Although nitrogen fertilizers are expensive and unavailable in adequate quantities in many developing countries, relatively high rice yields can be obtained by optimizing spacing of rice plants in the field. We studied the interrelationship of nitrogen level, plant population and distribution pattern, and rice yield.

Three field experiments were conducted at the Gezira Research Station (13°30' – 15°5'N and 32°30' – 33°30' E) during 1977-79. Climate is semiarid and most rains (350-400 mm) fall during July and August. Soils are dark cracking Vertisols with 40-65% clay content.

Effect of nitrogen level, interrow spacing, and seeding rates on grain yield and some major yield components of irrigated dry seeded rice IR2053-206-1-36 in a semiarid environment in Sudan Gezira (av of 3 seasons 1977-79).

	Yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain weight (g)
<i>N (kg/ha)</i>				
60	4.2	343.2	70.8	23.17
120	4.8	386.6	78.3	23.64
180	6.4	411.1	80.1	23.91
<i>Interrow spacing (cm)</i>				
15	5.3	464.9	75.1	23.56
20	5.6	367.0	76.8	23.56
25	5.5	310.1	77.4	23.60
<i>Seeding rate (kg/ha)</i>				
50	5.5	358.7	82.2	23.48
100	4.4	382.8	76.5	23.64
150	5.5	400.5	70.5	23.60
S. E.	0.024	5.43	1.42	0.096

Treatments were 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha as urea; 15, 20, and 25 cm interrow spacings; and 50, 100, and 150 kg seeds/ha. Treatments were grown in a randomized complete block design with

four replications. Land was prepared dry by plowing, disc harrowing, and leveling, then was divided by heavy ridges into 3.8 × 8.0 m plots. Immediately before seeding, 6.2 kg P/ha as superphosphate